

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Study of biomechanics in violin performances with kinect and its relationship with Sound

Pablo Fernandez Blanco

Supervisor: Alfonso Pérez-Carrillo

Co-Supervisor: Mario Ceresa

June 2017

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Study of biomechanics in violin performances with kinect and its relationship with Sound

Pablo Fernandez Blanco

Supervisor: Alfonso Pérez-Carrillo

Co-Supervisor: Mario Ceresa

June 2017

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Motivation	1
1.2	Objectives	2
1.3	Hypothesis	3
1.4	Structure of the Report	4
2	State of the Art	5
2.1	Control	6
2.2	Posture and kinematics	9
2.3	Mapping sound control	15
2.4	Timbre description	17
2.5	Motion capture	20
3	Methods	22
3.1	Materials	22
3.1.1	Kinect	22
3.1.2	OpenSim	26
3.2	Design of the experiment	28
3.2.1	Dataset description	29
3.2.2	Baseline	30
3.2.3	Data acquisition	30
3.2.4	Feature extraction	31
3.2.5	Visualization	32

3.2.6	Segmentation	32
3.2.7	Data post processing	33
3.2.8	Output	36
3.2.9	Classification	37
3.3	Feature Extraction	37
3.3.1	Kinect	37
3.3.2	OpenSim	47
3.3.3	Audio Features	50
4	Results	53
4.1	First results	53
4.2	Kinematic results	53
4.3	Audio results	55
4.4	Kinematic and audio results	56
4.5	Feature selection results	57
5	Discussion	58
5.1	Discussion	58
5.1.1	Accuracy of the system	58
5.1.2	Meaning of the results	59
5.1.3	Relevance of the results	59
5.1.4	Medical doctor's comments	60
5.2	Conclusions	61
5.2.1	Personal conclusions	62
5.3	Future work	62
	List of Figures	64
	List of Tables	66
	Bibliography	67

Acknowledgement

First of all I would like to express my sincere thanks to my project supervisor Alfonso Pérez Carrillo, for all the time spent and for his valuable and constructive suggestions during the planning and development of my research project. His willingness to give his time has been much appreciated. Thanks for the support and for providing everything that was needed for the thesis.

Thanks to Mario Ceresa for his collaboration and assistance on those technical issues that required consultation, for his interest and encouragement in this study.

I would also like to thank Xavier Serra for accepting me in the master and for allow me to be part of the MTG group these two years, where I have felt very comfortable and I have been able to meet and work with people with great talent and where I think I have learned a lot.

I would like to thank the economic support received by the Maria de Maeztu scholarship, for selecting me as a beneficiary and, in this way, believing in me to carry out this project. This work was part of the TELMI project and I would also like to thank all its members.

I would also like to extend my thanks of those who have been involved during my training process and specially during my Master degree and that have made this project possible, to all those friends who have made suggestions, corrections and constructive critiques.

To finish, I would like to thank my family and my friends for all their unconditional support in all my projects.

Abstract

Playing a musical instrument is a highly complex activity, which requires a combination of mental and sensorimotor skills acquired during a long learning trajectory. Traditional music performance pedagogy is mostly based on imitation and feedback on the performance through semantic metaphors and imagery that attempt to explain an acoustic quality or a physiological aspect of the performance such as the posture or the feeling of movement. Such an approach is based on subjective and vague perception that, in many cases, result in frustrating lack of progress to chronic problems, forced breaks from performing during extended periods or even career-ending injury.

The long-term aim of this research is to study the scientific and technological challenges around the analysis and modeling of human motion in musical practice as a sensory-motor activity and involves the acquisition, description, storage and analysis of datasets of motion and audio data captured during real performances. More specifically, this work deals with the measurement and description of the kinematics and dynamics of the human upper-body motion during violin playing. A model of expert performers is built as a reference to compare with and automatically evaluate amateurs.

Human body motion is typically measured with camera based systems or with wearable inertial sensors technology (e.g. accelerometer, gyroscope) attached to the body. Both techniques, along with bio-mechanical models, can be used to extract features such as joint angle, posture, and joint rotation speed as well as many others which could be used for improved performance coordination to reduce the risk of injury through the measurement and feedback of prolonged joint extension and angular rotation intensity. In this work, we aim to develop low-cost implementations, using off-the-shelf technology, namely RGB-D cameras, to make the system available to a large potential user group. In general, the accuracy of low-cost systems is low. However with the advent of recent consumer level 3D cameras such as the Microsoft Kinect, body motion tracking becomes feasible.

Motion of the Violinist Upper-Body is acquired by means of a Microsoft Kinect Camera programmed using the provided C# SDK, which is able to track the position of the human body articulations and bones.

Based on the position of these joints, we estimate two type of features. First, kinematic features such as angles between bones, joint positions, displacement, speed and acceleration and second dynamic features (i.e. muscle forces in motion). Dynamic features are estimated by fitting the previously computed kinematic features against a bio-mechanical model. Kinematics allows to analyze motion and pose of violin performers and dynamic features are important in order to detect over-use and help prevent possible muscular injuries. The fitting with the bio-mechanical model is done with the OpenSim software.

Statistical analysis and machine learning techniques are used to build a reference model of expert performers that can be used to compare with amateurs and to give feedback and automatic evaluation of any performance.

In this work we aim to characterize violin performances in terms of kinematic and dynamic features of the human body and to build a reference expert model that allows to automatically classify between experts and amateurs. By means of the reference model, we can additionally measure how close to the reference a new performance is and give as feedback an automatic rating of its quality.

We have recorded a small database of experts, amateurs and non-violinists and our model is able to correctly classify 90% of the cases.

Keywords: Violin, kinematics, dynamics, measurements, RGBD camera

Chapter 1

Introduction

Playing an instrument is a difficult activity. Usually, people go to classes to learn and they need many observations from more experienced people to guide them on how to play. The teacher's comments are based on their observations. This more traditional pedagogy continues working well nowadays but the use of modern technologies to learn music is more common in our times. From tutorials to programs used to follow a sheet and that measure how well the user plays. One of the big problems in musicians are injuries. Learning to play an instrument often requires repeating many times the same action, and not doing it properly can lead to various physical problems resulting in an impediment or in a frustration. The intention of this project is to carry out a study that creates a model about how to play an instrument, using the violin as a case-study. Usually, these types of projects are made with very expensive machines or sensors that must be attached to the instrument, and that tends to annoy the musicians. We propose working with a low-cost system, using the Kinect tool.

1.1 Motivation

Modern technologies offer us a lot of possibilities. The main goal of this research is to use the technology to improve the quality in the musical study, focused on violin as a case study. Being more specific, we try to use low cost systems to inform

the person who plays the result of their interpretation. These low-cost systems are accessible to a larger number of people, fact that motivates us to develop the greatest number of technologies with such systems to make them more profitable. In addition to providing this detailed information that increases the quality of musical study, a major motivation of this study is to avoid unhealthy habits and avoid injuries. For this reason, the project is carried out in collaboration with the department of biomechanics of the Pompeu Fabra University of Barcelona, with the aim of study the forces that the body makes when playing the violin. We think that getting a low-cost and not intrusive system for this purpose can be very useful, as there are many musicians who have muscle problems, making it difficult to achieve their goal and even in some cases being the cause of frustration or impediment of progress. Finally, this research has been carried out in close collaboration with the H2020 TELMI project coordinated at UPF and in collaboration with Università de Genova (Italy), Royal College of Music (London), Highskillz (Portugal) and Saico (Spain).

1.2 Objectives

The principal goals of this research work are:

- Implement a prototype to empirically measure human body motion and sound based on the kinect camera and microphones, in order to identify the main factors that affect when playing the violin.
- Understand the differences among violin performers with different skill levels and train the system so that it can automatically classify a performer into skill levels.
- Provide feedback to the musician about their performance.
- Perform a study of the forces involved in this action by fitting motion data to bio-mechanical models. Understand the forces that cause the most common injuries and can warn the users when they do more strength than necessary.

- Compute audio features relevant to the performance quality.
- Synchronization of multimodal data (audio and motion)
- Create models to advise the user by comparing his performance against a reference performer.

1.3 Hypothesis

Based on our intuition and visual and auditory evidences, we can differentiate between a person who knows how to play the violin and another who does not. Although it is also true that most of the persons are not able to affirm all the elements that change between one and the other. It is for this reason that we think there is a difference between groups of people. Even if you have more musical knowledge you can differentiate between a no-experienced violinist and a professional. Based on the previous reasons, we approach the problem by analysis of performers with different levels of experience and we look for patterns to characterize the most appropriate way to play this instrument. This reasoning leads, however, to a controversial concern: is there a single correct way to play the violin? Is it the same for everyone? It seems evident that there is not. Along with the field of sport, a few years ago a kinematic study like ours was done studying in depth the way of running of the ten fastest sprinters of the world. The final conclusion was that each one ran in a separate way. Can we then deduce that it is not possible to extract a single ideal model? Maybe not, but, however, we believe that there is a set of common characteristics that everyone performs in the same way (following the sport analogy, all sprinters bend their knees and run forwards, for example). Otherwise, it would be impossible for a teacher to advise a student to improve: "You should raise more your shoulder". But, why? We refer then, to those common characteristics of a professional interpretation that we want to find and from which we hope to obtain a model to advise the players. Additionally, there are also many differences in the sound quality, which we will also try to differentiate by computation of relevant audio features able

to correctly classify a good interpretation and find their relationship with motion features.

1.4 Structure of the Report

The report is divided in four sections: In the first one, we present the state of the art of our work. Then we show our methods and materials, explaining in detail the design of the experiment and justifying our choices. Then we present our results and finally, in the last chapter, we extract some conclusions and we try to analyze them.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

The main motivation of this work is to understand how affects the posture and gestures of a player in the way they played and the kind of sound. What I'm look for in this research is to establish a relationship between the position and the sound of the musician. Often, when someone is told to change positions he realizes that his sound changes, but cannot describe how or if change is good or bad. In addition, I am very concerned for my personal knowledge of analysis and understand the different timbres in the instrument. The study of that topic can help me in future work and research. I think that a work like that may be very beneficial to help novices players to avoid possible injury or bad posture that can be a handicap for their performance. It can also help professional people who want or need to change their position. But basically, what I want to demonstrate is that there is a change in the sound. In this way, we could prove that the position is directly related with timbre, which is our main hypothesis. We propose the case-study of the violin. In the case of the violin we think that the sound is directly related to the cinematic of the musician. For this reason, we will develop our study with the Microsoft tool Kinect, that can identify the parts of the human body. Besides, it's a low-cost tool, characteristic that could make our system more accessible to the people. There is not a lot of work done in this field so specific, but there are papers about other fields that are directly related. In these fields, we will base our State of the art.

This may seem a problem, because it is always difficult to start an experiment on which there is little documentation, but also work on a new topic in which we can provide new findings and conclusions seems very stimulating. The thesis involves the following topics, in which we have divided the previous study: control measures in musical instruments, posture and kinematics, mapping control and sound and timbre description. Also, we highlight aspects of computer vision to recognize the points in the study of posture.

2.1 Control

The acquisition of musical gestures and particularly of instrumental controls from a musical performance is a field of increasing interest with applications in performance transcription, performance modeling, mapping strategies between gestures and sound, sound synthesis or automatic graphics rendering of musical performances among others. The direct way for the acquisition of such gestures is through measurement of physical variables with sensors on the instrument or on the performer. The process usually involves the use of expensive sensing systems and complex setups that are generally intrusive in practice. There have been several studies on the controls that affect the sound produced by a violin. In [1] we have an example of some measures of physical controls of the violin: In this work they capture bow position, bow to bridge distance, bow force and bow velocity. It seems that these 4 elements help a lot to describe how you play a violin and the type of sound achieved. In this work they use tools that are incorporated into the violin as force gauges, or sensors that measure the position of the bow. In 1 we can observe this sensors and the measured parameters.

There are other studies, like [2], where they have used other kind of sensors. In this case they have used emf to acquisition of violin instrumental gestures. We can see the main diagram of the study in 2

We can see that the majority of features are the same like those of study [1], adding String estimation, acceleration and finger position estimation. This system is used

Figure 1: Violin sensors and the measured variables

Figure 2: Main scheme of the study [2]

in our university, and if we are able to extract some of these features with the kinect, we think that it would be very interesting to compare the results by taking the emf as a ground truth and see if those acquired with kinect make sense and analyze their accuracy. Another system widely used to measure this type of features is Vicon, for example in [3], where you can measure forces, accelerations and speeds. In addition, bowing angles (tilt, skewness and inclination) are included in this study 3.

Figure 3: Tilt, skewness and inclination

The system is really powerful, but it needs to record video with 6 Vicon cameras, sound, and it needs to put markers on the violin. Nevertheless, we think that it would also be interesting to analyze and / or combine our project with others of this type. Another type of sensors used are the accelerometers as in example [4], or in our project TELMI, where is used this type of sensor attached to the bow of the violin. Most of the cases use markers of some kind to identify the violin and draw features related to the position of this object. These points do not disturb us with kinect but our intention is to build something that at the same time is low-cost is zero intrusive, since we know that many musicians are not in favor of adding objects or sensors to their instrument. We have also worked on the controls of other instruments, like the guitar in [5] and in [6]. In particular we find this second interesting in which the audio is also analyzed. The following algorithms have been used: YIN (temporal), sigmund Max MSP object (spectral) and MIR toolbox pitch detection algorithm (used with the autocorrelation-method). In this case the sensors are different but we can add that they use an RMC pickup. Another interesting study focused on the guitar is [7], in which a gesture caption system was done based on capacitive sensors and Arduino. It should be added that the guitar is an instrument less expensive than the violin, and there are good guitars cheaper than a moderately good violin. That's why we believe that musicians are less skeptical when they have to put some external element in their instrument (in fact, they are often familiarized to being amplified electronically). The last work we have read and in which we want to make more emphasis is on Indirect Acquisition of Violin Instrumental Controls from Audio Signal with Hidden Markov Models [8]. Results show that the presented method is an accurate, non-intrusive and

low-cost alternative for instrumental control acquisition of a previously calibrated violin and recording device. This paper reports a novel indirect acquisition method for the estimation of continuous violin controls from audio-signal analysis based on the training of statistical models with a database of previously recorded violin performances. The database contains synchronized streams of audio features and instrumental controls. Audio signal was captured with a vibration transducer built into the violin bridge, and instrumental controls were measured with sensors. The controls include bowing parameters (played string, bowing velocity, bowing force, and bowing distance to the bridge) as well as fingering position. Once the model is trained for a specific violin, they can perform indirect acquisition from analysis of the signal captured with its embedded transducer without the need for the sensors any more. The statistical methods used are Hidden Markov Models (HMM) with observation distributions parameterized as Multivariate Gaussian Mixtures (GM). HMMs provide a means for note recognition and following and parameter prediction is based on GM regression. Diagram of the method it's represented in 4

Figure 4: Flow graph of the model and the prediction

The equipment for this experiment is the same of the one in [2].

2.2 Posture and kinematics

Our research requires a preliminary study of some experiments that have studied posture and kinematics, two vital elements to understand and analyze in order to play any instrument. We can classify all instruments by the way that they have played. There are some in which the body movement is essential to produce sound, as the battery or the violin, and others where it is not so important, as wind instruments, which is the air that produces the sound and body movement acts as

controller (touching pistons for example). In [9], they analyze if biomechanical skills needed for performance on the violin can be accurately and objectively characterized and generalized and if these data can be used to inform performance pedagogy to maximize efficiencies and minimize injury. From this study, we can extrapolate the conclusions for the violin-case and understand the importance of posture in the educational context to improve efficiency, which is what we tried to show in our experiment. In addition, reading this paper I thought that the topic of minimize injury may be interesting to study too. Thus, our purpose will be to maximize the efficiency and effectiveness of skill acquisition while minimizing the incidence of injury.

Musical performance shares many characteristics, including health risks, in common with other skill-oriented activities [10] and [11]. For example, commonalities between sports and musical performance are obvious, particularly in the area of biomechanics. For that reason, we will ask every subject in the experiment if he/she had some problems and we will try to observe the relation with the gestures and posture.

Artist teachers are trained as musicians, not scientists. Consequently, approaches to teaching the biomechanics of musical performance may be based on subjective and vague perceptions of what works in the personal experience of the teacher, rather than an accurate understanding of the principles of human movement [12].

The competitive nature of music and the fact that artistic success or failure is often determined by micro-incremental perceptions of talent or ability means that an emphasis on immediacy of skill acquisition to gain an edge, sometimes at the expense of careful pedagogy, is often a natural consequence.

Systematic collaborative inquiry into the biomechanics and physiology of musical performance holds the potential to significantly improve performance pedagogy by seeking answers to important multi-faceted questions: (1) Can biomechanical and physiological functions that contribute to success in musical performance be objectively and accurately identified, described, and generalized (i.e., characterized) using scientific methods? (2) How can objective scientific data be used to inform musical

performance pedagogy to maximize skill acquisition while minimizing injury?

We also need which factors we are going to study. For string instruments, it is generally understood that three physical parameters influence the bow use/tone relationship: (1) pressure on the string; (2) bow speed; and (3) bow contact point on the string. Less well documented are the relationships among these factors. Changes to bow pressure affect tone colour (timbre) more than volume (other factors remaining constant), and, conversely, changes to bow speed affect volume most noticeably.

Acquiring technical skill without injury, three factors influence the relationship between muscles loading and overuse (repetitive use) injuries: load quantity (intensity), quality, and duration (time). In our study, we are going to focus on the quality aspect, but we have to keep in mind the other aspects (duration and quantity) at the moment of extract conclusions.

Results suggest that static loads are significantly more dangerous than dynamic ones. If static loading is a known factor associated with repetitive stress injuries, then a logical prevention strategy would be for the performer to consciously choreograph movements that minimize static conditions or postures.

Results indicated identifiable and describable motor control patterns for shoulders and elbows, joints that dominate gross motor control, to be consistent among participants and therefore generalizable. Conversely, no consistency was found for wrists, joints responsible for fine motor control movement (see 5). This was true for both arms.

The results are really close to the results that we will have, so we think that I will be a nice work to compare both Works. Another study similar to our is [13], where they have investigated how motion at proximal arm joints influenced the precision of bow movements in novice learners and experts. The authors found that learning to play the violin was not associated with a release or freeing of joint degrees of freedom. Instead, learning was characterized by an experience-dependent suppression of sagittal shoulder motion, as documented by an observed reduction in joint angular

Arm			Flex/ext		Abd/add		Rotation			
			<i>M</i> (°)	<i>SD</i> (°)	<i>M</i> (°)	<i>SD</i> (°)	<i>M</i> (°)	<i>SD</i> (°)		
ROM	Left (near-static)	Shoulder		31	8	13	5	22	7	
		Elbow		101	6					
		Wrist		29	22	8	9	0	7	
	Right	Shoulder	Lateral	Max.	87	9	35	4	80	9
			G-string	Min.	64	4	10	3	63	4
			Medial	Max.	103	10	42	4	89	9
			E-string	Min.	95	9	15	3	73	5
		Elbow	Lateral	Max.	104	9				
			G-string	Min.	38	4				
			Medial	Max.	104	9				
			E-string	Min.	47	4				
		Wrist	Lateral	Max.	21	18	22	12	18	11
			G-string	Min.	-26	16	-14	8	2	6
			Medial	Max.	18	17	24	16	16	12
			E-string	Min.	-23	15	-16	13	3	5

Figure 5: ROM of the different angles of the shoulders, elbows and wrists

amplitude. This reduction in the amplitude of shoulder flexion–extension correlated highly with a decrease of bow-movement variability. The remaining mechanical degrees of freedom at the elbow and shoulder showed patterns of neither suppression nor freeing. Only violinists with more than 700 practice hr achieved sagittal shoulder range of motion comparable to experts. The findings imply that restricting joint amplitude at selected joint degrees of freedom, while leaving other degrees of freedom unconstrained, constitutes an appropriate strategy for learning complex, high-precision motor patterns in children and adults. The findings also highlight that mastering even seemingly simple bowing movements constitutes a prolonged learning process. As Visentin said in [9], With respect to the joint coordination of the bowing arm, trained violinists show consistent patterns of shoulder and elbow motion, whereas the wrist joint motion of each player appears to be highly individualized. It is a study very similar to ours. It studies the differences between people regarding the time they are studying, research similar to ours. It also measures how the violinists’ abilities improve with the hours of study. It would be interesting to measure this change, but we do not have this time. In addition it includes some graphs of the trajectories of the movements like the one that we show below in 6 that seem interesting to visualize how are the actions of the violinist.

We analyze also a real-time System for teaching in violin in [14]. The main idea is integrating the vibrotactile feedback and the motion capture. In our case we don’t need a neuro feedback but we want to know the advantages of build a real-time model

Figure 6: Graphics of three violin players during the performance: A beginner child, and advanced child and an expert. The y axis shows the right shoulder angle and the x axis shows the right elbow angle

that help teaching with motion capture They describe the ongoing development of a system to support the teaching of correct posture to novice violin players, focus on the movements of the violin players (8-12 years). Novice players have to develop a wide range of cognitive and physical skills including: reading music notation; counting notes and rests in order to play in rhythm; learning where to place their fingers on the instrument; and listening to whether the note they are playing is in tune. Furthermore, has to develop precise control of body movements, as well as great postural awareness. Their system aims to help the players maintaining good posture while playing and controlling bowing movement (that part doesn't affect us).

Learning by observation and imitation is challenging for novice players because they often do not know what they are looking for nor how to translate what they see into their own body movements. It is very difficult for the teacher to give verbal feedback during a dynamic bowing action and so generally comments are made after the movement is completed.

Important requirements for the current application were that the system should operate in real-time, be easy to set up and use, and be portable to allow field studies in environments familiar to the children. For these reasons, we chose an IGS-190-M mobile motion capture system from Animazoo. This system consists of small inertial measurement units (a combination of three-axis accelerometers, gyroscopes and a magnetometer) suitable for measuring 3D orientation. The sensors are attached to a Lycra body suit and the data are transmitted by a wireless processing unit to a receiver connected to a computer. The positions of the joints are computed using a hierarchical model of the human skeleton, which can be fitted to the subject. In the current setup, we used a total of six sensors for effective tracking of the bowing arm, along with the position of the instrument.

The i-Maestro project uses an Optical motion capture system, where reflective markers are attached to the bow and the violin to track their movement. An image of a 3D animated violin in motion is shown to the player on a screen, including some additional data on their performance. It was found that musicians had difficulties absorbing the visual information while playing, and preferred auditory feedback.

The issue of cognitive overload in music teaching Systems is also explored in the work of Sadakata and colleagues [15] who emphasize the value of tools that aid the communication between the teacher and the student during a lesson. They designed visual abstractions relating to expressiveness of rhythmic patterns and used this in a study involving amateur musicians. They found that the limits of working memory mean that a player can only effectively deal with a restricted amount of information in the auditory and visual modalities. It is quite easy to fall into a trap of displaying too much information to a student and thereby interfere with the cognitive processes involved in the activity of music making.

2.3 Mapping sound control

One of our objectives is to map the sound of the violin with the gestures that are captured. We know in advance that these results cannot be more accurate than other experiments that capture more controls in a more precise and with more direct influence in the audio, such as the pressure on the string or the bow to bridge distance. To analyze tasks carried out in this sector, nothing is better than read the doctoral thesis of our supervisor, in [16], that talk about enhancing Spectral Synthesis Techniques with Performance Gestures using the Violin as a Case Study. In this work, they investigate new sound synthesis techniques for imitating musical instruments using the violin as a case study. Based on the characteristics of the main vibrating elements of the violin, they divide the study into two parts, namely bowed string and violin body sound radiation. With regard to the bowed string (in which we will focus), they are interested in modeling the influence of bowing controls on the spectrum of string vibration. To accomplish this task, they have developed a sensing system for accurate measurement of the bowing parameters. Analysis of real performances allows a better understanding of the bowing control space, its use by performers and its effect on the timbre of the sound produced. Besides, machine learning techniques are used to design a generative timbre model that is able to predict spectral envelopes corresponding to a sequence of bowing controls. These envelopes can then be filled with harmonic and noisy sound components to produce a synthetic string-vibration signal.

There's also a work [17], in which the goal of the research is to model the relationship between actions performed by a violinist and the sound which these actions produce. Violinist actions and audio are captured during real performances by means of a newly developed sensing system from which bowing and audio descriptors are computed. The model is driven by a continuous sequence of bowing and fingering controls and is able to generate their corresponding sequence of spectral envelopes. The model is used for synthesis, either alone as a purely spectral model, by filling the predicted envelopes with harmonic and noisy components, or coupled with a concatenative synthesizer, where the predicted envelopes are used as time-varying

filters to transform the concatenated samples. This analysis is important to better understand the relationship between the actions and the timbre, and to help selecting features for training the model. The influences of bow velocity and bow-bridge distance on string vibration were established in the classic work by Helmholtz [18] and the effect of bow force is reported in [19]. We can see these graphics in 7

Figure 7: RMS energy - RMS energy vs velocity, tilt - tilt and dynamics, bow force - dynamics and pitch - pitch sharpening graphics

Their audio is analyzed in the spectral domain using an algorithm based on the pitch-based phase-locked vocoder]. The sample rate of the recordings is 44 100 Hz and the analysis window is a Blackman–Harris window of size 2048 samples. The data acquisition rate is determined by the Polhemus system (240 Hz). And the timbre representation it's done in this way: Harmonic and residual components are both represented as the energy in 40 overlapping frequency bands with centers following a logarithmic scale (see fig x). The overlapping factor is 50%. The energy of each band is estimated as the average of the corresponding frequency bins, weighted by a triangular function. The determination of the band centers is based on auditory models, more precisely on the Mel scale (8).

In addition, they analyze a factor that I think I can use at various points in my studio: The Input parameter size(IPS): The input parameter space is a subset of

103	508	1117	2033	3412	5485	8604	13296
171	611	1272	2266	3761	6011	9396	14487
245	722	1439	2518	4141	6582	10255	15779
326	843	1621	2792	4553	7202	11187	17181
413	975	1819	3089	5000	7874	12198	18703

Figure 8: Band centers based on the Mel scale

the entire playable region determined by the coverage of the scores and by the specific bowing technique of the recorded Player.

2.4 Timbre description

The study of timbre in the field of music information retrieval is very important. Perceptually relevant timbre parameters are needed as indices for content-based search of targeted timbres in very large sound databases, as well as for automatic categorization, recognition, and identification schemes for musical instrument and environmental sounds [20].

The literature in this field is broad and exhaustive, as Geoffroy Peeters explain in [21]. One consequence of that is a decrease in the comparability of results. Further, in the machine-learning literature, it is not easy to establish whether differences across studies in classification performance are caused by a change in the sound-descriptor system or by differences in the mathematics of the classification algorithms. A second consequence of the variety of approaches to acoustical characterization is that no single study adopts a truly exhaustive system for characterizing acoustical signals.

I have found The Timbre Toolbox, that implements several different classes of audio descriptors related to the spectral, temporal, spectrotemporal, and intensive properties of the signals. We can distinguish three main properties of an audio descriptor: (1) the temporal extent over which the descriptor is computed (time varying, in a specific region in time, such as the sustain, or global descriptors, in the whole duration of a sound file), (2) the signal representation used to compute it (the temporal energy envelope, the short-term Fourier transform, the output of an auditory model, and sinusoidal harmonic partials.), and (3) the descriptor concept described. In 9,

we can see the descriptors of the Timbre toolbox.

	Audio descriptor	Units	Abbreviation	Input representation
Global descriptors	Attack	s	Att	Temporal Energy Envelope
	Decay	s	Dec	
	Release	s	Rel	
	Log-Attack Time	log(s)	LAT	
	Attack Slope	a/s	AttSlope	
	Decrease Slope	log(a)/s	DecSlope	
	Temporal Centroid	s	TempCent	
	Effective Duration	s	EffDur	
	Frequency of Energy Modulation	Hz	FreqMod	
	Amplitude of Energy Modulation	a	AmpMod	
Time-varying descriptors	Autocorrelation (12 coefficients)	-	AutoCorr	Audio Signal
	Zero Crossing Rate	s ⁻¹	ZerRate	
	RMS-Energy Envelope	a	RMSEnv	Temporal Energy Envelope
	Spectral Centroid	F	SpecCent	STFTmagnitude (STFTmag) STFTpower (STFTpow) ERBft (ERBft) ERBgammatone (ERBgam) Harmonic
	Spectral Spread	F	SpecSpread	
	Spectral Slowness	-	SpecSlow	
	Spectral Kurtosis	-	SpecKurt	
	Spectral Slope	F ⁻¹	SpecSlope	
	Spectral Decrease	-	SpecDec	
	Spectral Rolloff	F	SpecRollOff	
	Spectro-temporal variation	F	SpecVar	
	Frame Energy	J	FrameErg	
	Spectral Flatness	-	SpecFlat	
	Spectral Crest	-	SpecCrest	
	Harmonic Energy	a ²	HarmErg	Harmonic
	Noise Energy	a ²	NoiseErg	
	Noisiness	-	Noisiness	
	Fundamental Frequency	Hz	F0	
	Inharmonicity	-	InHarm	
	Tristimulus (3 coefficients)	-	TriStim	
Harmonic Spectral Deviation Odd to even harmonic ratio	a	HarmDev OddEveRatio		

Figure 9: Audio descriptors available in the Timbre Toolbox library

It is important to see the correlation and clustering of these descriptors. The paper also makes a study of this. In 10 we can see it, based on [22]

Figure 10: 3D graphics of the correlation and clustering of these descriptors

This analysis was carried out by focusing on the hierarchical clustering model of the correlational distance between descriptors. Firstly, two independent clusters emerged that overall group together spectral descriptors computed using the same time-varying operator. As such, one cluster mostly contained median descriptors for spectral time-varying descriptors [e.g., Centroid (med) and Kurtosis (med)], whereas another cluster included interquartile range spectral descriptors [e.g., Centroid (iqr) and Kurtosis (iqr)]. A third large cluster included the vast majority of the temporal descriptors (e.g., log-attack-time) and the energetic descriptors [e.g., NoiseErg (iqr)

and TotErg (iqr)]. A final large cluster included descriptors measuring mostly signal periodicity or lack thereof (e.g., f0 and noisiness). The descriptors that have been grouped together have very small distances between them (for example SpecCent/SpecSlope or HarmErg/NoiseErg). Based on this result, we conclude that the Timbre Toolbox provides informationally rich descriptions of the sound signals. The largest of these groups included (1) descriptors quantifying the central tendency of time-varying spectral properties; (2) descriptors quantifying the temporal variability of time-varying spectral properties; (3) descriptors quantifying global energetic properties and descriptors for the properties of the energy envelope; and (4) descriptors of the periodicity of the sound signal. From a practical point of view, these results suggest that multiple descriptive statistics of the time-varying descriptors should be taken into consideration because of their ability to capture different aspects of the sound signals. Although characterizing sound signals with the highest possible number of descriptors will surely maximize the amount of information extracted concerning the sound signal, it is important that we, as researchers, carry out a principled selection among descriptors based on the quantification of their informational overlap. For these reasons, we should be particularly wary of choosing a very large number of clusters if this means separating moderately to highly correlated descriptors.

Once we analyze the possibilities we have to analyze the timbre, we have based on the work of Good Sounds [23], to be able to extract through the algorithm YIN the following parameters.

- Pitch stability, based on the Std of the f0
- Dynamic stability, studied with Std of the power in dB
- Pitch clarity, approximated pretty well with the aperiodicity

Then we want to compute too the timbre stability and richness. The richness is not so easy, because there's not too much bibliography in this field and we will need

to create a data base, annotate it, and determine what features are related to this richness. So, we will just compute the timbre stability, following the paper X, in which we can see this approach.

2.5 Motion capture

Motion capture (mocap) can be defined as the creation of a three-dimensional (3D) representation of a live performance [24]. This is achieved by tracking and recording the positions, angles, velocities, accelerations and impulses of a performer at a high rate of speed through sensors attached to or pointed toward the body to provide an accurate digital representation of the movement. Each motion capture system is comprised of a hardware component that measures movements of the performer, and a software component that calibrates the system and records the data. There are three main types of motion capture systems: (1) Mechanical, (2) Magnetic, and (3) Optical.

1. Mechanical: are often referred to as exoskeleton motion capture systems due to their external structure. These typically rigid metal or plastic structures have articulated joints with potentiometers that directly measure a performer's joint angles as he or she moves. One of the main advantages of this direct measurement system is that no cameras or other sensors are needed. The main disadvantages to the system are that the performer is limited to the degrees of freedom of the structure and the location of the sensor placement is fixed. Ex. Gypsy 5 by Meta Motion.
2. Magnetic: operate by measuring the low-frequency magnetic field generated by a source transmitter to its receiver. There are two types of magnetic systems. Direct current (DC) systems; which use square pulse waves, and alternating current (AC) systems, which use sine pulse waves. One of the major advantages of these systems is that each sensor transmitter/receiver pair can capture six degrees of freedom (x, y, and z position coordinates as well as yaw, pitch and roll orientation angles) instead of the more common three degrees of free-

dom (x, y, and z position coordinates). However, the sensors in the system, especially in AC systems, can be susceptible to environmental metal, magnetic fields and electrical sources such as rebar walls and floors, lights, cables, monitors and computers in the area. Ex: SICIB, by Morales-Manzanares et al. [25].

3. Optical: use multiple high-speed cameras or video cameras to triangulate the position of each marker on the performer. The advantages of these systems are that they are capable of very high sampling rates, have a much larger capture volume than that of magnetic systems and that as many markers as needed can be used. One disadvantage is that the cameras need a clear line of sight, and markers can be occluded if the cameras are not placed correctly. Nintendo Wii is an example.

We are going to work with kinect. A more cost-efficient option can be found within the modern multimedia cameras such as the Microsoft Kinect and Leap Motion, which both utilize infrared (IR) technology in order to recognize the 3D space, according to the orientation of specifically projected IR patterns. For instance, Hantraku and Kaczmarek have experimented with Leap Motion for sound synthesis as well as an assistive performance tool for modulating effects in real-time [26]]. Furthermore, Kinect has been used in research projects in the context of musical interfaces, similar to the Air Violin project [27], as well as for gesture analysis in music conducting [28], and music performance [29]. Other works with kinect are: Kinect based interactive music application for disabled children [30] or Motion Analysis of Music Ensembles with the Kinect [31], where they present a method for motion analysis of musical ensembles based on head tracking with a Kinect camera.

Chapter 3

Methods

We divide this chapter in three parts. First of all, we present the materials that we use in our work, and analyze how the tools work. The second part is focused on the design of the experiment and the implemented methods. Finally we will see how the features are computed in the section Feature extraction.

3.1 Materials

The main materials we have used are Kinect and OpenSim, and we analyze them in this section.

3.1.1 Kinect

Kinect sensor's frequency is 30 FPS (frames per second) and the resolution of the camera is 640x480 pixels. The depth sensor has two depth ranges, namely the default range and the near range. The former range detects distances from 800 mm to 4000 mm and the latter from 400 mm to 3000 mm. See 11.

The positive z-axis extends in the direction in which the Kinect is pointed.

Figure 11: Distance from the sensor in the default and the near range

How Kinect measure distances

Kinect integrates an infrared sensor, along with a depth processor. The visible area is called "field of view". The depth processor produces depth frames. Each depth frame is a grid of 512x424 points. The Kinect SDK is then feeding the depth frames to a powerful body-detection algorithm. The algorithm identifies 25 human body joints, represented in 12, and calculates their coordinates in the 3D space. In addition to these 25 points, Kinect offers us the 4x4 rotation matrix, which tells us how much has rotated the object in each angle.

Every single joint has 3 values: X, Y, and Z. It is projected in a Cartesian coordinate system. The (0, 0, 0) point is the position of the sensor. Every other point is measured in terms of the position of the sensor.

- X is the position in the horizontal axis in meters.
- Y is the position in the vertical axis in meters.
- Z is the position in the depth axis in meters.

X and Y are fairly easy to understand. Z value is not the linear distance between the point and the sensor. Instead, it's the distance between the point and the plane of the sensor. It's like having a virtual wall right in front of the Kinect. The Z value is the vertical distance from that wall.

Figure 12: Kinectv2 joints

However, when we develop a Kinect app, we use computer monitors. Somehow, we have to project the 3D points on the 2D screen space. There are 2 screen-spaces:

- Color Space: is a set of coordinates in the 2D Color space. The Color space is a 1920x1080 frame. A ColorSpacePoint only has two coordinates: the X coordinate defines the distance from the left edge of the frame, and the Y coordinate defines the distance from the top of the frame.
- Depth/Infrared Space: is, again, a set of coordinates in the 2D Depth space. The Depth space is a 512x424 frame. A depth point has X and Y values, just like the color points. The Depth space is equivalent to the Infrared space, so you can use the same type of points for both.

Obviously, points in the 2D space only have X and Y values, measured in pixels. So, we have to convert meters to pixels. The “body” variable represents the tracked player. The “Position” property is a set of X, Y, and Z coordinates in the 3D space. The “Z” value is the distance between the player and the plane. Many studies have

used the Spine Base joint as a reference, since it's the most reliably-tracked joint, and it's also closer to the center of mass.

Measuring the distance

The distance between the player and the device is represented by a mathematical vector. The length of a vector is given by the formula below:

$$\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$$

- To measure the distance between the player and the plane of the sensor, we just use the Z value as-is.
- To measure the distance between the player and the sensor, we calculate the length of the corresponding vector.

3D reconstruction

It's possible that the violin affects too much to the tracking of the interesting points in our system. One possibility is to do a reconstruction of the 3d-space and with the help of the color of the violin, detect the object and extract it of the image in order to reanalyze it with the Kinect without the violin.

Discussion

The angles are easier to capture when its wide range of movement it's bigger.

There exist two main causes of divergence between the results obtained by the two compared systems, problems, one is the bad motion tracking of hip adduction and ankle angles, and the other is the difference of angles at the beginning of the capture. After observing the skeleton animation together with the original video, it is concluded that several causes can yield the problems mentioned before. The possible causes are the following: Quick and sudden motion inaccurate scaling of the model, need for better post-processing, occlusion (segments not visible by the cameras) and starting with a T-pose cause a variation of the initial position if the

model is not well scaled. It seems that moving quicker, generally does not affect the accuracy of the results. In order to do accurate motion captures with the Kinect system, the studied motion should be performed smoothly and it is better when joints have a wide range of motion.

3.1.2 OpenSim

Musculoskeletal modeling and dynamic simulation have recently emerged as powerful tools to uncover the biomechanical causes of movement abnormalities and to design improved treatments. OpenSim is a powerful and freely available tool for modeling and simulation of movement. Users of this technology address fundamental issues in movement science and focus on critical areas of rehabilitation medicine, including stroke, spinal cord injury, cerebral palsy, prosthetics, orthotics, and osteoarthritis.

In this section we present the tools that interest us more for our research.

Scaling

The purpose of scaling a generic musculoskeletal model is to modify the anthropometry, or physical dimensions, of the generic model so that it matches the anthropometry of a particular subject. Scaling is one of the most important steps in solving inverse kinematics and inverse dynamics problems because these solutions are sensitive to the accuracy of the scaling step. In OpenSim, the scaling step adjusts both the mass properties (mass and inertia tensor), as well as the dimensions of the body segments. Scaling can be performed using a combination of two methods:

1. Measurement-based Scaling: This type of scaling determines scale factors for a body segment by comparing distance measurements between specified landmarks on the model, known as virtual markers, and the corresponding experimental marker positions
2. Manual Scaling: This type of scaling allows the user to scale a segment based on some predetermined scale factor. Manual scaling is sometimes necessary

when suitable marker data are not available, or if the scale factors were determined using an alternative algorithm.

Inverse Kinematics

Kinematics is the study of motion without considering the forces and moments that produce that motion. Thus, to perform kinematic analyses, such as inverse kinematics, mass and inertia properties are not needed. The purpose of inverse kinematics is to find the joint angles of the model that best reproduce the experimental kinematics of a particular subject. In this tutorial, the experimental kinematics used by the inverse kinematics tool are based on experimental marker positions. The inverse kinematics tool goes through each time step, or frame, of recorded motion and computes the set of joint angles that put the model in a configuration that "best match" the experimental kinematics. OpenSim determines this "best match" by solving a weighted least squares optimization problem with the goal of minimizing marker error. Marker error is defined as the distance between an experimental marker and the corresponding virtual marker. Each marker has an associated weighting value, specifying how strongly that marker's error term should be minimized in the least squares problem. In each frame, the inverse kinematics tool solves for a vector of generalized coordinates (e.g., joint angles), q , that minimizes the weighted sum of marker errors.

Inverse dynamics

Dynamics is the study of motion and the forces and moments that produce that motion. Thus, to perform dynamical analyses, such as inverse dynamics, estimation of mass and inertia is required. The purpose of inverse dynamics is to estimate the forces and moments that cause a particular motion, and its results can be used to infer how muscles are utilized for that motion. To determine these forces and moments, equations of motion for the system are solved iteratively. The equations of motion are derived using the kinematic description and mass properties of a musculoskeletal model. Then, using the joint angles from inverse kinematics and experimental ground reaction force data, the net reaction forces and net moments

at each of the joints are calculated such that the dynamic equilibrium conditions and boundary conditions are satisfied

Moment of forces

Inverse dynamics methods gives us the moment of forces, so we must analyze what a moment of force is. In physics, a moment is a turning effect of a force. It is an expression involving the product of a distance and a physical quantity, and in this way, it accounts for how the physical quantity is located or arranged. We can see the diagram in 13. Moments are usually defined with respect to a fixed reference point; they deal with physical quantities as measured at some distance from that reference point. For example, the moment of force acting on an object, often called torque, is the product of the force and the distance from a reference point. In principle, any physical quantity can be multiplied by distance to produce a moment; commonly used quantities include forces, masses, and electric charge distributions.

Figure 13: Draw to understand the moment of force variable

The unities of the moment of forces are Nm.

3.2 Design of the experiment

In this chapter, we will explain in detail how the experiment has been carried out, and will justify and analyze each part.

3.2.1 Dataset description

During the research, we performed 3 different tests: the first, with Kinect1, the second when changing to Kinect2 and the final, with which we present the results. Obviously, the first two have been used to test code problems and to check the system and implement improvements. With these tests, we have also realized the difference between subjects and the tests that we could do to have a varied dataset and with which we could visualize differences and create a model. In conclusion, our final dataset is formed by:

- 5 experts, who play every day and who dedicate themselves to music
- 5 amateurs (they have played in the past, but they have left or do not play regularly).
- 6 people who have never played the violin.

In this way, we can divide the dataset into two subclassifications:

- Professional, amateur and beginner
- Violinist (professional and amateur) and non violinist (beginner)

These two subclassifications have been made to analyze if the differentiation between violinists and non-violinists is much more evident than the division between the 3 classes of experience.

The samples we have recorded for each violinist are composed by 14 bows per string (G, D, A, E). Each bow is formed by four quarter-notes in time 80 bpm. The notes they have to play are the open strings. We have done this to focus on the study of the right arm, because with the Kinect we cannot capture the actions of the left one. In future studies, we can expand this study, to find the differences that exists when the person has to change the string that is playing. The tempo has been chosen in order not to be too slow or too fast and can be reproduced by all the people who perform the experiment.

3.2.2 Baseline

In 14 we show the flow diagram that follows our experiment.

Figure 14: Flow diagram of the experiment

We can see that at the beginning takes place the acquisition of the data with the Kinect. With the raw data provided, we calculate the features of angles, with which we calculate those of dynamic features and those of movement. At the same time we synchronize it with the audio acquired, from which we also get the necessary features. Then we do all the tasks of post processing and finally we carry out the classification, which will serve to create the model and try to relate the movements to the sound.

3.2.3 Data acquisition

The data of our experiment are collected with two devices: the Kinect v2 (15) and the Zoom recorder (16).

Figure 15: Kinectv2 sensor

From the Kinect we extract the raw data (which gives us the 3d coordinates of the identified joints (17)), that we synchronize with the audio of the recorder.

Figure 16: Zoom recorder

Figure 17: Kinect joints

3.2.4 Feature extraction

When extracting the data, the first thing we do is to carry out the most important of the synchronization: we create a timestamp that synchronizes all our features. With Visual Studio, we capture the angles and it generates a mot file that will be used to calculate moments of forces with OpenSim. We also compute different csv with the features (together and separated) in order to build a final csv to do the classification. At the same time, we also extract the joints data in the appropriate format to be able to upload the datapack automatically to Repovizz (visualize). In

the next chapter, we describe this section deeper.

3.2.5 Visualization

As we have explained, when processing the data of the Kinect we keep a datapack with the synchronized data to upload to Repovizz. Thanks to this tool we can visualize (all synchronized) the video, skeleton, audio and all csv with different calculated features. The main idea of using Repovizz was to make an analysis of the different subjects in the preliminary tests and to be able to understand which were the factors that changed more between the different subjects. Thanks to this study, for example, we realized the importance of the use of the bow: while the most experienced violinists use a wider range of the bow, correctly distributed at a temporal level, thus achieving a more stable speed. Instead, people who do not know how to play use a much smaller section of the bow. For this reason, we decided that it was also an interesting feature to analyze, as others that have emerged from this visualization and may help future research to find other differences. Besides, we realized that it is also a good teaching tool: we know that it is very useful to record the sound when we play to be able to analyze it afterwards. For this reason, we think it is very interesting to have a video audio recording and skeleton that serves the students to visualize after playing, even the teachers to explain in a more graphical way what they want to convey. Even if there is some angle that you want to correct you can use the visualization of the features to see that particular aspect as it evolves over time.

3.2.6 Segmentation

One of the most important parts that we perform in the post-processing is the segmentation in arcs. When doing the first recordings, we realized that the best option to compare violinists would be to compare each bow as an isolated action. In this way, the comparison is much more accurate, but we lose the information that exists in the change of arcs, that is the attack of each note (reason for which we have not calculated any audio feature related to the attack of the note). It

may also be interesting to do this study on future occasions. At the beginning, we performed this segmentation by analyzing the maximum and minimum of the angle of the elbow, which changes direction when the direction of the arc changes. This way worked very well with experts, because the movement was very clear and could be segmented perfectly. But with people who did not know was very complicated because often this angle did not oscillate so much, it remained static and the peaks were not clear enough. We can see an example of this comparison in 18.

Figure 18: Left elbow angle during a performance of an expert (upper graph) and a beginner (low-side graph)

When computing the bow distance (see next chapter), we realized that this feature was much better for segmenting the arcs, as we can observe in 19. All subjects change the direction of the bow when the bow changes. For this reason, we use this feature to segment each interpretation in the 14 bows of each subject.

3.2.7 Data post processing

Once we have all the features calculated we need to prepare our data to be classified.

The first step we do is a smooth, that soft the curves of the graphics, by which we managed to eliminate some of the noise we captured with the Kinect. We have

Figure 19: Graph of the bow distance

been testing different smooth factors until getting the right one so as not to lose information but to properly smooth the curves of the graphs. Then, we have to normalize our data.

Normalize

Once all the interpretations have been segmented, we have to normalize them to train the classifier and all the features must have the same weight. To do this normalization we need to know the maximum and minimum of each feature, what we know as range of movement (ROM). For kinematic features, it is easy to choose these values, analyzing the physical limit of the body, but both the features of speed, acceleration or force are not obvious. To calculate the ROM of each feature we have performed a function that, for each feature, crosses the middle part of each subject and returns the maximum and minimum. We analyze the intermediate part to avoid interferences that may exist at the beginning and at the end of the samples. However, there is often an undesirable peak, which is why we have created a clipping function that eliminates these values that are far from the ROM and therefore do not make sense to us and identify them as noise. Once we have the ROM of each feature, we normalize all features between 0 and 1.

Preparing data for classification

The last scheme for preparing the data is the one showed in 20.

Figure 20: Flow diagram from the features to the classification

The last step to prepare the data is to know how we want to analyze them. We have two strategies for analyzing the data:

- Make the histogram of each feature in each arc.
- Divide the use of the arc into 10 parts and analyze the mean and standard deviation of each feature in each of these ten parts

The justification for studying the data in this way is to eliminate the time factor in the analysis. We explain below the two methods implemented:

1. Histograms: When making the histogram of all the features in each bow, we can see how each angle in each ROM is divided in each interpretation. That is, we can know how to distribute each feature along the bow action. We have performed histograms with 10,20,50 and 100 bins. In the results section we will present the results of each one and we will choose the optimum, because we need enough sensitivity to differentiate between subjects, but at the same time, if we have too many bins, the classification will be too specific for each subject. Thus, the final amount of features to be sorted by each bow is: 30 features x nbins
2. Division of the bow in 10 parts: To do this, we also use the bow distance feature. Knowing that the bow measures 65 cm, we divide the bow into 10 sections of 6.5 cm. We analyze each frame and classify it in the corresponding

group. Unlike the other classification, this one is made of all the interpretation. The output we have is composed by 30 features, multiplied by the ten sections and from each we extract the mean and variance. Thus, the final amount of features to be sorted by each subject is: 30 features x 10 parts x 2(mean and std) In 21 and 22, there's an example with the Boxplot tool of Matlab comparing a professional with a non-violinist:

Figure 21: Boxplot of the elbow angle of a professional player

Figure 22: Boxplot of the elbow angle of a beginner player

3.2.8 Output

The outputs to train the classifier are:

- Audio Features

- Pitch stability
- Dynamic stability
- Pitch clarity
- Timbre stability
- Kind of musician
 - Violinist/Non violinist
 - Professional/Amateur/beginner

3.2.9 Classification

The last goal is to get the machine to rank as accurately as possible and to inform us of the difference between classes so that we can report the differences between the person playing and the people who know how to play well.

3.3 Feature Extraction

In this section, we explain how we compute the features of kinect, OpenSim, and the audio features.

3.3.1 Kinect

As we have seen in the state of the art, Kinect is able to automatically recognize some points of the human body. This will be the starting point of our features. Thanks to these joints, we are able to extract some parameters that will be used to characterize the interpretations of violinists.

What features do we need?

When we want to characterize a body movement, we ask ourselves: what parts of the body do they take part in? What angles can describe this movement? Are there redundant angles? What we want is to have as few angles as possible to describe the movement of the arc. The joints that we have decided to study are those of

the center of the body (spine base, spine center), and the 3 that form the right arm (right wrist, right elbow and right shoulder). We also use the joint 'left wrist' to simulate the violin (line between the neck and left wrist).

Main angles

To know which are the angles that better and more effectively describe the movement of a violin bow we have used two strategies:

- First, we used the tool created by the MTG Repovizz, which allows us to observe data from different synchronized sources. For this, we dedicated time to the automatic creation of a datapack, adapted to the format of Repovizz, that allowed to visualize the skeleton of the kinect, the video of the violinist, the graphs of the calculated angles and to hear the synchronized audio. We consider that this tool has been very useful to be able to observe after the recordings the movements of the skeleton and to be able to examine in detail the parameters that define the movement.
- One of the main objectives is to use the calculated angles to reproduce the movement in a biomechanical model of the upper right part of the human body. What we have used has been reverse engineering: we have seen an example of inverse kinematics for our model. Given some concrete points (not the ones provided by Kinect), it calculates the angles that are produced in this model. There are some such as deviation and flexion of the wrist, or rotation of the forearm, which we are not able to compute with points provided by kinect. But with the joints that gives us Kinect we can calculate four angles that, in our opinion, define in sufficient detail the movement of the player actions. These are: shoulder elevation, shoulder azimuth, elbow flexion and elbow azimuth. Now we will define these angles and explain how we calculate them.

Shoulder elevation:

This angle (23) could be understood as the angle of the axilla (assuming that the side of the body is parallel to the vector that forms the column). To calculate this,

Figure 23: Scheme of the shoulder elevation angle

we create two vectors in three dimensions: the first, the column, using the spine and spine shoulder points and the second, the vector of the humerus, which is determined by the right shoulder and right elbow points. Then, we calculate the angle between these two vectors and we already have the angle we want.

Shoulder azimuth:

Figure 24: Scheme of the shoulder azimuth

This angle (24) is more difficult to explain, because it occurs on the x-z axis and is more difficult to understand (unlike the previous one, which being on the x-y axis is much more visual). In this case, we have recalculated the humerus vector, but the other vector is perpendicular to the column, on the x-y axis. That is, the vector that

form the right shoulder and left shoulder (assuming they are at the same height). If we compute the angle formed by these two vectors, we have the shoulder azimuth.

Elbow flexion:

Figure 25: Scheme of the elbow flexion

This is the easiest angle to explain. The angle (25) is formed by the vectors of the humerus and the forearm (vector from right elbow to right wrist).

Elbow azimuth:

Figure 26: Scheme of the elbow azimuth

Besides being the most difficult to explain, this has been the most difficult to extract and the last we realized that we needed. It is directly related to the string that is played and can be useful in other works to identify which string is playing the violinist. To calculate this rotation (26), we have created a 3d plane defined by

three points (right wrist, right elbow and right shoulder). We have extracted the normal line to this plane and we have calculated the angle with respect to the x-axis of the kinect ($x = 1, y = 0, z = 0$)

We consider that with these 4 angles, we can describe the movement of the bow of the violin in a satisfactory way. In addition, as explained in the introduction of the section, are the features with which we feed our biomechanical system, as explained in the next chapter.

Speed and accelerations

Other parameters that may be useful to characterize the model are the speed and accelerations of the points that move. These features are taken from the joints that we consider that move in a more meaningful way, which are the right wrist and right elbow. The first method we used to calculate these features was to calculate the instantaneous value. For each sample, we calculated the distance that had crossed the point in the space and the time that had passed from the last frame and we made the division.

But the results were inconsistent and had a lot of noise. This was because the time elapsed was very small (about 30 ms) and the distance measured was small. Since the resolution of the kinect is in cm, many times there was no variation between frames and others the noise created peaks that did not correspond to the observed movement. The solution applied was to store the joints measures in each of the three dimensions (x, y, z) and store it in a vector, along with the elapsed time. At the end of the recording, we made a smooth of it, which softens the trajectory of the points to eliminate the noise. When doing this operation, the results are similar of the ones in 27 and 28.

We can appreciate the periodic movement, where every time there is a change of bow direction the velocity tends to 0, accelerates and remains constant during the arc. At the same time in the graph of acceleration we can see this variation of speed with respect to time: when the speed decreases, it is negative and after 0 in speed, the acceleration increases until the speed remains more or less constant and

Figure 27: Velocity graph

Figure 28: Acceleration graph

acceleration tends to 0.

Rotations

Kinect for Windows provides joint orientation information for the skeletons tracked. Kinect provides information about bone rotations. This rotation works in a hierarchical order: each segment has rotation data with respect to the parent bone, which

Figure 30: Scheme of the three parameters of the rotation for each bone

Use of the bow

This feature is especially meaningful and we have to explain it in detail. At first, we did not intend to analyze this characteristic, because we focused on the movements of the body. Also, with the Kinect we are not able to identify the elements that do not belong to the human body. However, when we analyzed the first samples, we realized the importance of the distance from the bow to the strings of the violin and how different it was between subjects who had more and less experience: the more experts make a wider use of the bow, distributing it in a balanced way in the execution time of each note, thus achieving a stable and rich sound. The more novice or with no experience, use a much smaller part, playing a much more unstable sound. Then, we realized that we could invent a line in space that could be quite effectively approximated to the line of violin strings. This is the one formed by the points of the neck and the left wrist. In 31, this line is represented with a white line.

Figure 31: Draw of our approximation of the bow. The white line represent it

Obviously, it is an approximation and can give errors. But it seems a good way

to calculate this distance. Then, we identify the point of the right wrist and we calculate the minimum distance of a 3d point to a straight line 3d.

This way of calculating the distance of the bow has 2 inconveniences: we assume that the point of contact of the hand and the bow is the right wrist joint (there is a margin of about 5 cm from one to another) and we assume that the angle that forms the strings and the bow is always 90 degrees (if it were not 90 degrees the previous formula would not be true because we would be calculating the shortest distance and in this case would not be true). Despite these two inconvenient, we can deduce that the problem is the same for all subjects and therefore this measure is useful for the study We then compared the POLEMUS system to analyze the differences in the measure of this distance (32 and 33).

Figure 32: Graphic of the bow distance computed with kinect

We can see that we lose information in the extremes. We can also see the 5-10 cm of margin that is, difference that is due to the measurement of the wrist that we have explained before. Although there is difference, we think that the difference is not so much and can be a very useful feature to analyze.

Figure 33: Graphic of the bow distance computed with polemus

Segmentation

In addition, this last feature is the one we have used to segment the bows of the violinist. At the beginning, we used the angle of the elbow for this, but the inexperienced people had a lot of noise and it was not useful to segment with that feature, since it was not stable. Instead, the distance to the bow always changes when changes the notes, even if you do not know how to play the violin. This makes segmentation much faster and more efficient.

We have to add that this process has been monitored because in some cases there was an extra peak because of the noise and we needed that the segmentation be precise to train the classifier. In future work, we have to work to make this method more robust. Although we consider that it already works very well, using a minimum separation between peaks and smoothing the signal, we must implement extra methods to avoid the false peaks, and we can do the automatic segmentation, fact that would be very useful to get this analysis done in real Time.

Other features

However, during the investigation, we realized that there were a number of parameters that were redundant but could be useful for other things such as avoiding vices. For example, measure the depth of the elbow with respect to the axis of the body. We have had the opportunity to talk to some teachers and expert violinists (see discussions) who explain us that, for example, having the elbow behind the body is an incorrect posture. This feature could be useful to alert people who have problems of this type and want to correct them, or avoid unhealthy habits. Other features of this type that we have extracted are the height of the shoulder and the height of the elbow.

Kinect1 vs Kinect2

Our study started with Kinect1 and in the middle process we discovered version 2 and we changed. This second version has less noise and more joints. This noise reduction also helps us to avoid in a more precise way the interferences caused by the violin and that creates problems to identify the joints near to the instrument. When changing the machine, we had to change the code: for example, the rotations worked differently and the systems to capture audio had other methods. But we can compare some results to see the difference between one system and another to be able to estimate how much quality difference there is and analyze whether it is worth switching to version 2 if we have the first.

In 34 we can see a comparison between computed speed with Kinect1 and Kinect2. We can see that Kinect2 are less noisier than Kinect1.

3.3.2 OpenSim

With OpenSim we can calculate the moments of force necessary to make a certain movement. There are many models of various parts of the human body. Since we only wanted to work with the part corresponding to the right arm, we have found a model that works only with this part of the body. 35 is a picture of our model.

Figure 34: Velocity of the elbow graphics comparing the accuracy of Kinect1(left) and Kinect2 (right)

Figure 35: Picture of the model with we work in OpenSim

OpenSim is designed to work with very precise position markers. This information is used to perform the inverse kinematics process, by which it can calculate the angles that form the distinct parts of the model. This step is the one we perform with the Kinect, and we can calculate these angles. A good future experiment would be to compare our system with the markers and analyze the accuracy of our method over the other. The next step is to use these angles to calculate the moments of forces that are necessary for perform this action. This is done using the inverse dynamics method, which returns a list with the moments of forces that we will analyze in the next section. There are two more options in OpenSim that can help us in our investigation, scalling and calculate forces, which could be interesting but we have not carried out for the following reasons:

- **Muscles forces** provide the solution of less energy, making the values suppose

little extra pressure in the muscles, which seems unrealistic. That is why we have thought that moments of forces are much more reliable and provide us with more realistic information that interests us more than the muscular forces.

- **Scaling**, because being a section of the body we had no method of knowing how much this section weighs alone. It would be interesting to find a solution to this problem because the biomechanical experts that we consulted affirm that this factor is important, and if we incorporate it, the results of these forces would be very reliable.

Here is the list of the moments of forces provided by the model used:

- sternoclavicular (2moments)
- unrotscap (2moments)
- acromioclavicular (3moments)
- unrothum (3moments)
- shoulder
- wristhand (2 moments)
- rz
- 4 input angles (elbow flexion, shoulder rotation,shoulder elevation and humerus rotation).
- Pro supination
- Wrist deviation
- Wrist flexion

These inputs are coupled together with the angles of kinect and the calculated speeds and accelerations and all together will be the input vector of our system.

3.3.3 Audio Features

The two main motivations of the work are to create a biomechanical model that identifies the correct postures to play the violin based on the experts and to try to map these postures, angles, velocities, accelerations, forces ... with the characteristics of the sound. The first thing to keep in mind is that with Kinect we can not measure all the parameters that influence the quality of the sound. It is evident that the speed, or acceleration peaks, as well as the angle with which we scrub the bow, influence the sound. But other features, such as the pressure on the strings or the bow to bridge distance, also influence (as we see in other studies that we analyzed in the state of the art chapter). Based on the fact that the features we have are not all the necessary to fully understand the characteristics of the sound, we will study the recorded audio and try to correlate with the features extracted. The purpose of the audio analysis is to compute some parameters that can describe the characteristics of this sound. For this, we need to analyze some of the characteristics that determine how a violin note is. For this, we have been inspired by the tool developed by the MTG, Cortosia: A tuner that measured sound quality in 5 dimensions: pitch stability, dynamic stability, timbre richness, timbre stability and attack clarity. With these elements, they are able to recognize how good is a trumpet sound. In our case, we have used the next 4 features:

1. Pitch stability
2. Dynamic stability
3. Pitch clarity
4. Timbre stability

The first three are computed with the Yin algorithm, and the last one is calculated through the feature tristimulus, extracted with Essentia. In the follow lines, I explain in detail how I calculated each of them Pitch stability: Standard deviation of the f_0 returned by the Yin algorithm. Dynamic stability: Computed by using RMS value.

We compute the standard deviation of the power in dB. With this number, we know if the dynamic is stable or not. Pitch clarity: mean of the aperiodicity measure of Yin algorithm. This value shows how sure is the pitch that the algorithm is detecting: if it's not sure, value is high and the pitch is not clear, and if it's low, near to zero, the pitch is well identified and we can conclude that the pitch clarity is really good. With it we get a good measure of whether a pitch is more or less defined. Timbre stability: different with the previous 3, we have calculated this feature using tritstimulus, which we extract with Essentia. The tritstimulus returns 3 values and we have 2 ways to calculate it: taking the 3 values or only the first. The formulas used are:

$$Timbre_{stability} = \sqrt{Std_{trist1}^2 + Std_{trist2}^2 + Std_{trist3}^2}$$

Or just:

$$Timbre_{stability} = \sqrt{Std_{trist1}^2}$$

Analysis of the audio

Before relating the audio to the features of Kinect and OpenSim, we need to know if we are characterizing the sound well enough. For this, we need to compare the results between violinists and non-violinists and see if the system is able to recognize if a sound is from someone who knows to play the violin or from someone who does not know. We will also make this comparison according to the range of experience. If we hear the sounds of a professional and someone who has never played the violin the difference is evident. But we need to show that with these 4 features the system is able to differentiate between the classes that we want to associate with the movements. For this goal we have created a csv with the following structure

- Inputs
 - Pitch stability

- Dynamic stability
- Pitch clarity
- Timbre stability

- Outputs
 - Violinist
 - Experience

Chapter 4

Results

In this section we present the results obtained in the experiment and how we have reached them.

4.1 First results

As we have seen, we have 300 inputs in our classifier and we only have 224 cases of each string (16 people for 14 bows). With so many inputs, the classifier returned values close to 100%, but they were not relevant results. Due to the over-fitting of entry, we identified each specific case. For this reason, we apply PCA, to reduce the number of input dimensions to our classifier.

Filters have also been made to avoid noisy samples. It should be added that the system is well balanced and we have not had to balance it.

4.2 Kinematic results

To reduce the number of dimensions we apply PCA, an algorithm that is used to reduce the dimensionality of a set of data. The algorithms with which we have performed these classifications are svm, perceptron, random forest, and K-nearest neighbors. We have chosen them because we have analyzed similar studies in which they present results with these classifiers, a fact that makes us think that they may

be adequate to classify our classes. The first analysis we do is to see if we can classify between violinists and non-violinists with different components of PCA. Here is a table:

Table 1: Kinematic results SVM and perceptron

PCA	Violin SVM	Experience SVM	Violin percip	Experience percip
1	86.57 %	53.24 %	86.11 %	51.85 %
5	86.11 %	59.72 %	92.13 %	71.75 %
10	90.74 %	70.37 %	93.52 %	84.25 %
20	93.51 %	87.96 %	97.69 %	97.68 %
50	97.68 %	91.2 %	97.22 %	92.59 %
100	97.22 %	93.98 %	96.75 %	94.9 %

Table 2: Kinematic results Random Forest and KNN

PCA	Violin RandF	Experience RandF	Violin KNN	Experience KNN
1	83.8 %	56.02 %	83.8 %	56.02 %
5	93.06 %	81.48 %	91.2 %	80.56 %
10	94.44 %	87.5 %	94.44 %	86.11 %
20	96.76 %	91.67 %	99.54 %	95.83 %
50	97.22 %	91.67 %	99.07 %	93.98 %
100	97.22 %	91.67 %	98.61 %	95.37 %

The percentage indicates the correctly classified instances. We also extract the results to classify according to the experience of the violinist. In this result, we find interesting to include an example of the confusion matrix in which we can see that it is more confused between amateur and professional than with beginner. And we can see that the system differentiates professionals and nulls almost perfectly. This will be analyzed in the conclusions, but it seems obvious that there is more difference with the class that has never made this movement than between the two others, in which the violin (although at a different level) has been studied. We can observe how the percentage increases proportionally with the number of PCA components until it becomes stable (even lower). The top is usually in 20 components, although

the greatest increase is usually between 4 and 5 components.

4.3 Audio results

As we said before, we have done a parallel audio classification that tells us how capable we are of recognizing the kind of player just analyzing their audio. We have computed all these results 2 times, changing the stability formula. In the results, we show the timbre stability calculated with 3 components, and timbre stability computed with just 1 component. As in the previous section, here we show a table with the results differentiating between violinist or non-violinist.

Table 3: Audio Results with 1 component of tristimulus to compute timbre stability

Method	Violinist	Experience
SVM	83.33 %	61.11 %
Perceptron	88.43 %	65.28 %
Random Forest	87.96 %	72.69 %
KNN	88.43 %	68.98 %

Table 4: Audio Results with 3 components of tristimulus to compute timbre stability

Method	Violinist	Experience
SVM	83.79 %	58.33 %
Perceptron	90.74 %	67.59 %
Random Forest	87.96 %	75 %
KNN	72.69 %	87.5 %

As in this case there are only 4 inputs, we have not performed PCA. Due to the results are better with only 1 component of tristimulus, the next results are analyzed with this measure.

4.4 Kinematic and audio results

Finally, we present the results that combine all the features: kinematic and audio. We can see that results are not always better, especially when the PCA is enough to have good percentages only with the kinematic. This is because it classifies better than the audio, and adding these variables sometimes adds noise that confuses the classifier.

Table 5: Kinematic and audio results SVM and perceptron

PCA	Violin SVM	Experience SVM	Violin perc	Experience perc
1	86.57 %	52.77 %	85.65 %	53.24 %
5	86.57 %	59.72 %	93.51 %	73.14 %
10	92.59 %	70.37 %	95.37 %	87.96 %
20	97.22 %	88.42 %	96.29 %	95.83 %
50	98.15 %	90.74 %	98.15 %	93.05 %
100	98.15 %	96.29 %	98.61 %	94.44 %

Table 6: Kinematic and audio results Random Forest and KNN

PCA	Violin RandF	Experience RandF	Violin KNN	Experience KNN
1	79.63 %	56.48 %	79.63 %	56.48 %
5	93.52 %	81.02 %	91.67 %	82.87 %
10	96.3 %	88.89 %	96.3 %	87.5 %
20	97.22 %	91.2 %	99.07 %	96.76 %
50	98.15 %	92.13 %	98.61 %	93.98 %
100	97.69 %	92.13 %	98.15 %	93.52 %

Finally we show a graph 36 with a comparison between methods classifying among violinist and experience (all results are with PCA with 20 components and 1 component of tristimulus in timbre stability).

Figure 36: Graphic of the comparison between methods classifying among violinist and experience

4.5 Feature selection results

In the following table, we can see the first 10 values that the feature selection algorithm returns us.

Table 7: Feature selection

Kinematic	Audio	Kinematic and Audio
0.4215 Velbow-5	0.44 aperiodicity	0.4404 aperiodicity
0.411 Veלבow-3	0.341 dyn instab	0.4215 Veלבow-5
0.3984 Veלבow-2	0.296 Timbre instab	0.411 Veלבow-3
0.3654 sternoclavr3-9	0.259 pitch instab	0.3984 Veלבow-2
0.3485 unrothumr3-5		0.3654 sternoclavr3-9
0.3466 acromioclavr3-5		0.3485 unrothumr3-5
0.3364 unrotscapr3-7		0.3466 acromioclavr3-5
0.3331 Accwrist-2		0.341 dyn instab
0.3329 unrothumr3-9		0.3364 unrotscapr3-7
0.3243 acromioclav r3-6		0.3331 Accwrist-2

With this measure, we want to know which are the inputs that have more weight for our classifier. With this, we know which are the most important to classify, where we can appreciate more variation and consequently where there are the main differences between the different kind of players.

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Discussion

Before extracting conclusions, we will discuss the results and try to make sense of them.

5.1.1 Accuracy of the system

When we do an experiment like this, one of the first questions we ask ourselves is: how do we know if the results we are measuring are correct? And if so, how can we know the accuracy of these? In some cases, we can be guided by physical evidence, such as when measuring angles: we can know if they correspond to the movement performed more or less. Or velocities. Or if the biomechanical model moves in a similar way to the person who plays. However, how do we know how good these results are? For example, when doing the smooth, how do we know if we are only eliminating the noise of the kinect or are we losing information? The way to examine the benefits of our system is to compare them with a ground truth: alternative measures whose reliability has been demonstrated and in which we believe. Being a relatively new study there are not many results that we can compare. The only features we could compare are the distance to the bow and the speed of the bow (in our case the speed of the wrist, but we can assume that it is

the same). As we have seen, the speeds are similar and the distance to the bow is a reliable measure although it loses information at the extremes. We think that we can still improve these measures in the future but we are satisfied with the current measures. In addition, it is reasonable that a low-cost system is less accurate than a system that works with sensors and is much more expensive.

5.1.2 Meaning of the results

What does a 90% accuracy result mean? Our system can distinguish with this effectiveness between the different classes with the samples that we have. This indicates that there is an obvious difference between them, that we are able to identify with our data. With these results, we can classify a KNN, that builds a cluster with the professional violinists and violinists can be informed of how far they are from this cluster. The next interesting step would be to record more professional violinists and build a larger dataset. In addition, it would be interesting to analyze the differences and similarities between professionals to create a model based only on similar aspects that our professional dataset has and that we could consider as ground truth. For example, some professionals use a smaller angle than others in a certain section of the bow: this feature would not be an indicator since there are different ways of doing so. On the contrary, we would study common movements among professionals to base the model on these features.

5.1.3 Relevance of the results

There are several studies that study the controls on the violin. Even as we have seen in the state of the art, in the repercussion on sound. But there is no documentation on a study made for the study of violin with a low-cost system made with Kinect. In addition, all studies are focused on more precise sensors, forgetting the topic of posture (although there are some cases). However, in the posture section we added the study with OpenSim that we think that can be studied in future works. It would be interesting to develop a tool that will help prevent injuries to violinists. It would be necessary to do a study with biomechanical experts to confirm that the

force data are reliable (as we have analyzed, in this study we have not done the scaling, for example). Finally, we have achieved classifications with more than 90% accuracy and it is a good result, but we must not forget that we have only divided into 3 classes (2 in the case of violinist / non-violinist) and it would be appropriate to continue with the work to be able to divide in more levels (in which case, it seems obvious that the accuracy would be lower). And as we have already mentioned in the previous section, to base our model only on the common characteristics of the most expert people.

5.1.4 Medical doctor's comments

With the results obtained we asked what conclusions we could obtain. After drawing our own conclusions, we decided to look for people who might have knowledge of the subject and could give us another point of view. That's why we looked for and realized that there is a hospital specialized in musicians in Terrassa. And what better than to ask for opinion to a center of these characteristics that we have near? The team leader of the center, Dr. Jaume Rosset, agreed to hold an interview with us that gave us a very interesting point of view from which we can extract the following observations:

1. There is no single way to play an instrument. In parallel with the field of sport, a few years ago a kinematic study like ours was done studying in depth the way of running of the ten fastest sprinters of the world. The final conclusion was that each one ran in a separate way. Therefore, we can deduce that there is not a single way to play.
2. A musician does not always play in the same way. And the most important observation: musicians who tend to play always in the same way are more rigid, and therefore are less adapted to different circumstances and more likely to be injured. According to them it would be interesting to work this kind of flexibility. For example: get the same sound with two different postures. This way we would have a flexibility that they consider optimal to avoid injuries.

Our opinion is that this comment is very interesting and we could use our tool to make an application that works this kind of flexibility.

3. Finally, we explained the two most typical injuries in violinists, that we will try to analyze with the results of OpenSim.

5.2 Conclusions

We can conclude that our study has satisfactory results. We have done all the work we had planned (except for the mapping audio-movements) and we are satisfied that we could have done it in the estimated time. If we make a list of the functionalities of the system we have:

- We can track the human body holding a violin with a RGB-D camera
- Kinematic features, angles, bowing features are computed from the joint 3D position
- Fit with a biomechanical model to extract joint momentum (dynamic features) and muscle forces
- Automatic segmentation for each bow movement
- We can automatically classify between expert violinists and amateurs with high accuracy
- Automatic classification into different skill levels

The hypotheses that we had have been confirmed and we have been able to draw conclusions of the differences between the different violinists. Being critical, we think that the work is very broad and extensive and maybe we should have focused on fewer things and study them in more depth. But this makes a great possibility for future options, as discussed in the section on future work. We can also conclude that with Kinect, a low-cost system, more accessible than other systems, we are able to measure a large number of features that are relevant to understand the execution

of the violinists and that has a great future. We have also analyzed that Kinect2 offers better results than the first version and we recommend it for future studies.

5.2.1 Personal conclusions

As a personal conclusion, I think that this work has helped me a lot to learn a new topic from this field, to become a better researcher, to be restless and to seek solutions to problems. As a musician and engineer, I think the project is very interesting and I am very proud to have done it successfully. In the musical part, I have been able to extract audio features that are relevant and that describe quite well the sound. And I consider that the application of this study can be very useful for the study of violinists. In addition, I have learned to give a different approach to the study and have managed to improve my knowledge in the field of statistics or machine learning.

5.3 Future work

If we have the opportunity to continue the work there are several ways to continue. The first would be to expand the dataset: It seems evident that 16 users, divided into 3 classes are not enough to generalize an action as complex as playing a violin. We need lots of samples, especially of more professionals to be able to further dimension our model and to have more examples. In addition, to increasing the number of users, an option already discussed would be to expand the contents of the samples, not just record open strings. Even extend the study and examine the change of direction of the bow, to be able to analyze the attack of the notes, not just the sustain part. On the other hand, it would be interesting to go deeper into the study of detecting dangerous motions and static tensions that may cause injuries. So far, we have only calculated the different forces, but not the effect of these or the injuries they cause. It should be added that to study these types of effects, long studies are needed to see the long-term effect of movements. Speaking with the “Institut de l’Art” in Terrassa, we asked if it would be possible to record violinists who had problems or injuries. And they told us that recording an injured musician is like recording a cripple: you

will analyze the consequences of his injury, not the causes. We had the intention of map the sound with the movements. We have the intuition that the sound can be correlated with features more focused on stability, which could be extracted from the study in which we divided the bow into 10 parts. Another goal in the future is to do generative models. And it would also be very useful to be able to do the study in real time. This is necessary in the final product in which a violinist plays in front of the camera and receives immediate feedback. In addition, we could assign marks based on the quality of their interpretation (measuring the proximity to the model). Another observation we want to name is that we could use some results to make other types of applications: for example, to use this system to help the segmentation of notes (accompanying the onset detection, we could reinforce the algorithm with the changes of bow direction), or know which string is playing the violinist, thanks to the height of the elbow or the angle elbow azimuth, which is directly related to the string being played. Lastly, we think that it would be useful to construct an application in which the musician can create alerts, based on the teacher's observations, to avoid unhealthy habits. For example, if your teacher tells you mustn't raise your shoulder, but you are studying at home and you have the bad habit of raising it, when you are not concentrated. It would be extremely useful to have a configurable system in which you could adjust which is the maximum height of the shoulder (or the depth of the elbow, or any other characteristic) that you want to allow yourself.

List of Figures

1	Violin sensors and the measured variables	7
2	Main scheme of the study [2]	7
3	Tilt, skewness and inclination	8
4	Flow graph of the model and the prediction	9
5	ROM of the different angles of the shoulders, elbows and wrists	12
6	Graphics of three violin players during the performance: A beginner child, and advanced child and an expert. The y axis shows the right shoulder angle and the x axis shows the right elbow angle	13
7	RMS energy - RMS energy vs velocity, tilt - tilt and dynamics, bow force - dynamics and pitch - pitch sharpening graphics	16
8	Band centers based on the Mel scale	17
9	Audio descriptors available in the Timbre Toolbox library	18
10	3D graphics of the correlation and clustering of these descriptors	18
11	Distance from the sensor in the default and the near range	23
12	Kinectv2 joints	24
13	Draw to understand the moment of force variable	28
14	Flow diagram of the experiment	30
15	Kinectv2 sensor	30
16	Zoom recorder	31
17	Kinect joints	31
18	Left elbow angle during a performance of an expert (upper graph) and a beginner (low-side graph)	33
19	Graph of the bow distance	34
20	Flow diagram from the features to the classification	35

21	Boxplot of the elbow angle of a professional player	36
22	Boxplot of the elbow angle of a beginner player	36
23	Scheme of the shoulder elevation angle	39
24	Scheme of the shoulder azimuth	39
25	Scheme of the elbow flexion	40
26	Scheme of the elbow azimuth	40
27	Velocity graph	42
28	Acceleration graph	42
29	Rotation hierarchy in Kinect	43
30	Scheme of the three parameters of the rotation for each bone	44
31	Draw of our approximation of the bow. The white line represent it	44
32	Graphic of the bow distance computed with kinect	45
33	Graphic of the bow distance computed with polemus	46
34	Velocity of the elbow graphics comparing the accuracy of Kinect1(left) and Kinect2 (right)	48
35	Picture of the model with we work in OpenSim	48
36	Graphic of the comparation between methods classifying among vio- linist and experience	57

List of Tables

1	Kinematic results SVM and perceptron	54
2	Kinematic results Random Forest and KNN	54
3	Audio Results with 1 component of tristimulus to compute timbre stability	55
4	Audio Results with 3 components of tristimulus to compute timbre stability	55
5	Kinematic and audio results SVM and perceptron	56
6	Kinematic and audio results Random Forest and KNN	56
7	Feature selection	57

Bibliography

- [1] Askenfelt, A. Measurement of the bowing parameters in violin playing. ii: Bow-bridge distance, dynamic range, and limits of bow force. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* **86**, 503–516 (1989).
- [2] Maestre, E., Bonada, J., Blaauw, M., Perez, A. & Guaus, E. Acquisition of violin instrumental gestures using a commercial emf tracking device. In *ICMC* (2007).
- [3] Schoonderwaldt, E. & Demoucron, M. Extraction of bowing parameters from violin performance combining motion capture and sensors. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* **126**, 2695–2708 (2009).
- [4] Schoonderwaldt, E., Rasamimanana, N. & Bevilacqua, F. Combining accelerometer and video camera: Reconstruction of bow velocity profiles. In *Proceedings of the 2006 conference on New interfaces for musical expression*, 200–203 (IRCAM—Centre Pompidou, 2006).
- [5] Norton, J. C. *Motion capture to build a foundation for a computer-controlled instrument by study of classical guitar performance* (Stanford University, 2008).
- [6] Reboursière, L. *et al.* Left and right-hand guitar playing techniques detection. In *NIME* (2012).
- [7] Guaus, E. & Arcos, J. L. Analyzing left hand fingering in guitar playing. *Proc. of SMC* (2010).

- [8] Perez-Carrillo, A. & Wanderley, M. M. Indirect acquisition of violin instrumental controls from audio signal with hidden markov models. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing* **23**, 932–940 (2015).
- [9] Visentin, P., Shan, G. & Wasiak, E. B. Informing music teaching and learning using movement analysis technology. *International Journal of Music Education* **26**, 73–87 (2008).
- [10] Fishbein, M., Middlestadt, S. E., Ottati, V., Straus, S. & Ellis, A. Medical problems among icsom musicians: overview of a national survey. *Med Probl Perform Art* **3**, 1–8 (1988).
- [11] Robson, B. E. Competition in sport, music, and dance. *Medical Problems of Performing Artists* **19**, 160–166 (2004).
- [12] Brandfonbrener, A. G. Musculoskeletal problems of instrumental musicians. *Hand clinics* **19**, 231–239 (2003).
- [13] Konczak, J., vander Velden, H. & Jaeger, L. Learning to play the violin: motor control by freezing, not freeing degrees of freedom. *Journal of motor behavior* **41**, 243–252 (2009).
- [14] Van Der Linden, J., Schoonderwaldt, E. & Bird, J. Towards a real-time system for teaching novices correct violin bowing technique. In *Haptic Audio visual Environments and Games, 2009. HAVE 2009. IEEE International Workshop on*, 81–86 (IEEE, 2009).
- [15] Sadakata, M., Hoppe, D., Brandmeyer, A., Timmers, R. & Desain, P. Real-time visual feedback for learning to perform short rhythms with expressive variations in timing and loudness. *Journal of New Music Research* **37**, 207–220 (2008).
- [16] Pérez, A. Enhancing spectral synthesis techniques with performance gestures using the violin as a case study. *Department of Information and Communication Technologies* (2009).

- [17] Carrillo, A. P., Bonada, J., Maestre, E., Guaus, E. & Blaauw, M. Performance control driven violin timbre model based on neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing* **20**, 1007–1021 (2012).
- [18] Helmholtz, H. *On the sensations of tone* (Courier Corporation, 2013).
- [19] Meyer, J. The tonal quality of violins. In *Proc. Smac*, vol. 69 (1983).
- [20] McAdams, S. Recognition of sound sources and events. (1993).
- [21] Peeters, G., Giordano, B. L., Susini, P., Misdariis, N. & McAdams, S. The timbre toolbox: Extracting audio descriptors from musical signals. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* **130**, 2902–2916 (2011).
- [22] Peeters, G. A large set of audio features for sound description (similarity and classification) in the cuidado project (2004).
- [23] Romani Picas, O. *et al.* A real-time system for measuring sound goodness in instrumental sounds. In *Audio Engineering Society Convention 138* (Audio Engineering Society, 2015).
- [24] Menache, A. *Understanding motion capture for computer animation and video games* (Morgan kaufmann, 2000).
- [25] Morales-Manzanares, R., Morales, E. F., Dannenberg, R. & Berger, J. Sicib: An interactive music composition system using body movements. *Computer Music Journal* **25**, 25–36 (2001).
- [26] Hantrakul, L. & Kaczmarek, K. Implementations of the leap motion in sound synthesis, effects modulation and assistive performance tools. In *ICMC* (2014).
- [27] Fan, X. & Essl, G. Air violin: A body-centric style musical instrument. *Ann Arbor* **1001**, 48109–2121 (2013).
- [28] Sarasúa, Á. Context-aware gesture recognition in classical music conducting. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Multimedia*, 1059–1062 (ACM, 2013).

- [29] Hadjakos, A. Pianist motion capture with the kinect depth camera. In *Proceedings of the Sound and Music Computing Conference*, 303–310 (2012).
- [30] Kadakal, Y., Kivrak, H. & Kose, H. Kinect based interactive music application for disabled children. In *Signal Processing and Communications Applications Conference (SIU), 2014 22nd*, 453–456 (IEEE, 2014).
- [31] Hadjakos, A., Großhauser, T. & Goebel, W. Motion analysis of music ensembles with the kinect. In *Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression* (2013).